

MONITORING OF SKILLS AND SKILLS TRAINING OF MODERN INFORMATICS

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Abstract.

The introduction of ICT will undoubtedly lead to a radical change in the educational system, this process is carried out along with the revision of educational goals, which will lead to a change in the structural component of education, Modern Informatics the problem of finding the optimal solution for organizing the teaching process.

Key words.

ICT, Informatics and information technologies, professional skills, Modern Informatics, quality, education.

Informatics and information technologies (Informatics and IT) - is to ensure thorough mastering of information technologies and the processes of their use to the growing generation. The formation and growth of students' scientific outlook, ability to think logically, mental development, self-awareness potential depends to a large extent on information technologies. It is necessary for a person to enter into personal, socio-economic and professional relationships in his life, to take his place in society, to solve the problems he faces, and most importantly, to be competitive in his field and profession. must have basic competencies.

At the current stage of modern development of our society, high demands have been made by our president to create a new generation of educational literature and to improve the professional skills of professors and teachers in order to improve the quality and efficiency of education. Also, the penetration of ICT in every sphere of our society will undoubtedly lead to a radical change in the education system, this process will be carried out along with the revision of educational goals, which will lead to a change in the structural component of education. [1]. The problem of finding the optimal solution for the organization of the modern Informatics teaching process has not yet been fully resolved, despite the appearance of many methodological textbooks, teaching-methodical complexes and didactic materials. These educational materials and curricula (working

curricula) reflect the author's point of view, and although they are methodologically based, they do not create a complete picture of the given field of study. This is why different methods of teaching computer science have appeared.

As a solution to this problem, one of the approaches is based on the principle of integration, according to which it is necessary to use all educational-methodical complexes and information resources in the educational process, as a result, regardless of subjective conditions. A good educational and informational environment will be formed in science. The implementation of an integrated approach requires the development of a complex of educational programs for a continuous informatics course and the organization of a control system.

As a result, dynamic and flexible models of the organization of the educational process in the form of a script with a development direction are created. Within the framework of this model 65, an optimal teaching structure can be developed in terms of teaching content and organization. Knowledge is the most basic component of the educational process, and its correct organization at all stages of education ultimately determines the quality of education.

About information, information and knowledge. Information processes. Information quality indicators. Units of measurement of the amount of information: bit, byte, kilobyte, megabyte, gigabyte, terabyte, petabyte. Representation, storage, processing and transmission of information. About information technology. Types of information technology. Internal and external factors of information technology. Methods and means of information transmission. The role of information technologies in the information society. About information systems. Information society. Information culture. Legal basis of public information.

Material and technological foundations of the information society. Information resources of society, educational information resources. Internet, information security, law and ethical norms in the use of information. The role and importance of information in professional activity (as an example of various professional fields). Multimedia technologies. Office software package and its content. Document preparation. Text editors. Presentation and its creation.

Data warehouse. Spreadsheet editors. Graphic objects and methods of their representation on the computer.

In turn, the composition of the control process is as follows: A) Checking the results of training (correct or incorrect) and measuring them (in accordance with the accepted measurement system (rating regulation)); B) Viewing assessment as a process, during which students' behavior is monitored and compared with standard (sample) or accepted indicators; and treating assessment as an outcome.

It is appropriate to look at supervision not only as an assessment, but as a process that performs the following three types of tasks: 1) It controls the process of knowledge acquisition, that is, seeing mistakes, evaluating teaching results, correcting knowledge, skills and abilities. provides opportunities to perform correction tasks. 2) It educates the motivation to acquire knowledge and encourages creative activity. A properly organized control system makes it possible to instill a sense of responsibility for the results of training, to make efforts to correct mistakes; 3) It is a teaching and development tool.

A large part of the control process has a teaching and development character, because it explains the student's mistakes, explains what to do to download the learning material, helps to find the right answer. In addition, the student's personal qualities are developed: will, sense of healthy competition, striving for success. The classification of control methods (by the place of control, by the method of organization, by the method of obtaining information) can be adapted by science teachers, but is based on the traditional schemes presented in [2]. Various sources of information can be used, including [3], for classification based on the evaluation method and leading function. In the teaching of modern informatics, general teaching methods are used to perform the tasks listed above and adhere to the principles listed, including the type of control by the place of control at the educational stages (initial (like an incoming test), current (quick) control, final control (such as an exit test); according to the evaluation method (traditional evaluation system-evaluation in the form of 5 points, rating control system, "quality" technology is mainly an observation method; according to the control organization method (automatic, mutual assessment, teacher control, self-control; on the use of the leading function (diagnostic control, motivational control); on the method of obtaining information during control (oral method (i.e. different words roves, heuristic conversations, exams, discussions), written method, public methods (implementation of direct projects and presentations while observing the process of performing practical and laboratory work). Thus, the triple task of teaching is carried out in the process of supervision: education, development and education.

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